

APPENDICES

KAMPALA INTERNATIONAL UNIVERSITY (KIU) WESTERN CAMPUS (WC) RESEARCH ETHICS COMMITTEE (REC)

PO Box 71, Bushenyi, Uganda; Tel: +256 758 096 775
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APPENDIX I: INFORMED CONSENT DOCUMENT FOR PLANNING UNIT, PRODUCTION AND MARKETING, WORKS, EDUCATION SERVICES, HEALTH SERVICES, COMMUNITY BASED SERVICES, FINANCE, NATURAL RESOURCES, PROCUREMENT, NATURAL RESOURCES, INTERNAL AUDIT AND STATUTORY BODIES DEPARTMENTS

Study Title:

ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE AND EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE IN SELECTED LOCAL GOVERNMENTS IN WESTERN UGANDA

Principal Investigator(s): ASIIMWE AISHA

PhD PAM/8172/163/DU

INTRODUCTION

What you should know about this study

- You are being asked to join this research study;
- This consent form explains the research study and your part in the study;
- Please read it carefully; and take as much time as you need;
- You are a volunteer. You can choose not to take part; and if you join, you may quit at any time. There will be no penalty if you decide to leave the study.

Leave blank (for REC Office only):	For REC Office use only:
NAME OF REC CHAIR: <i>Prof. Ahmed Kiswezi</i>	APPROVAL DATE:
TELEPHONE: +256 772426581	APPROVED CONSENT REC VERSION
KIU REC STAMP:	NUMBER:
	PI's NAME:
	REC NO:

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Background to the study

This study is entitled “Organizational Culture and Employee Performance in selected local Governments in Western Uganda “this current study is going to take place in Kasese and Kabarole districts local governments in Western Uganda.

Purpose of the research project

The researcher shall consider 155 participants and will present a letter from Kampala International University and permit from the National council for Science and Technology to Kasese and Kabarole district local government authorities for permission to go ahead with the study and the participants shall fill in the questionnaire for three days.

Why you are being asked to participate

The participant is asked participate because he/she has valuable information the study can consider in order to improve on employee performance in Kasese and Kabarole districts local governments in Western Uganda.

Risks/Discomforts

There are no anticipated risks from participating in the study. The participants can be assured that no harm or discomfort will result from participating in this proposed study.

Benefits

The study participants especially the Administrators will indirectly benefit from the study findings if the developed model for employee performance is adopted by the local government. All employees in the twelve departments at each local government will benefit from improved performance which will be supported by the developed model.

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Incentives/Rewards for Participating

Every participant will be compensated for participating in the study with a monetary fee of 20,000/= Uganda shillings only. Therefore with a total number of 155 participants, three million, one hundred thousand shillings (3100, 000/=) will be put aside to cater for the compensation of research participants.

Protecting data confidentiality

All information gathered by this research will be kept anonymous and confidential. All information taken from the study will be coded to protect each participant's name. No names or other identifying information will be used when discussing or reporting data. The principal Investigator will safely keep all files and data collected in a secured manner. Once the data has been fully analyzed the questionnaires will be destroyed.

However, local Research Ethics Committee (**REC**) and Uganda National Council for Science and Technology (**UNCST**) are the only entities which may have access to private information that identifies the research participants by name.

Protecting participant privacy during data collection

The Self-administered Structured questionnaires shall only bare the initials of the names but not the full names of the respondents in order to protect their privacy.

Right to refuse/withdraw

Participation in this study is voluntary and any participant who is not comfortable with the kind of data being asked in the study can choose to withdraw at any time without any penalty this participant will still benefit from this study.

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What happens if you leave the study?

The participant may discontinue participation at any time, without penalty or loss of benefits.

Who do I ask/call if I have questions or a problem?

Please contact the **KIU REC Office** for any questions/problem on the addressed indicated below:

The KIU REC Chair

P.o Box 71, Bushenyi

Mobile: +256-772426581

Email: kiurec2017@kiu.ac.ug

Principal Investigator(s) contact and Email: ASIIMWE AISHA:.....0701133776

asiimwe.aisha@kiu.ac.ug.

What does your signature (or thumb print/mark) on this consent form mean?

Your signature on this form means that you have:

- Been informed about this study’s purpose, procedures, and possible benefits and risks;
- Been given the chance to ask questions before you sign; and
- Voluntarily agreed to be in this study.

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 Name of participant Signature of participant _____
 Thumb print Date

 Name of person obtaining _____
 Consent Signature _____
 Thumb print Date

 Names of witness _____
 Signature of witness _____
 Thumb print

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APPENDIX II: STRUCTURED QUESTIONNAIRE FOR PLANNING UNIT, PRODUCTION AND MARKETING,WORKS,EDUCATON SERVICES, HEALTH SERVICES,COMMUNITY BASED SERVICES,FINANCE NATURAL RESOURCES, PROCUREMENT,STATUTORY BODIES AND INTERNAL AUDIT DEPARTMENTS

Dear Respondent,

The following questionnaire has been developed to collect data for a study in fulfilment of the requirements for the award of a Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) degree. You have been selected to participate in the study owing to your eligibility. I will be very grateful for your cooperation and honesty in completing all items on the questionnaire. You are not required to indicate your name anywhere on the instrument for purposes of confidentiality. The instrument will be kept securely under lock and key by the researcher for at least three years. No unauthorized person will access the instrument except the researcher and the research supervisors. Hence your responses will be treated with utmost confidentiality. You will be given twenty thousand shillings (20,000/=) as compensation for participating in this current study. You will be required to fill this questionnaire within three days.

SECTIONA: PROFILE OF RESPONDENTS

Tick (✓) or write the ONE most appropriate response for each question.

1. What is your Gender?
a) Male b) Female
2. What is your Age group?
a) 20-30 b) 31-40 c) 41&above
3. What is your level of Education?
a) Primary b) O'level c) A' level d) Certificate
e) Diploma f) Bachelors g) Masters
h) Post Graduate Diploma i) PhD
4. For how long have you been working with this Local Government?
a) Less than 1-year b) between 2-3 years c) between 4-5 years
d) Above 6 years

SECTION B: Influence of Organizational Culture on Employee Performance

In this part the study attempts to assess the influence of Organizational Culture of employee performance in local governments of western Uganda.

Below are several statements on various dimensions of Organizational Culture on employee performance in local government.

Using the response scale below, indicate your response to these questions by placing a tick (✓) in the appropriate box under the appropriate number after that item.

1= Strongly Disagree, 2= Disagree, 3= Not sure, 4=Agree and 5= Strongly Agree

SECTION C: Communication patterns on Employee Performance

S/N	Statements/rating	1	2	3	4	5
1	In my organization, there is immediate feedback provided to employees' grievances	1	2	3	4	5
2	In my organization, there is frequency of communication on critical matters affecting employees in the Local Government	1	2	3	4	5
3	In my organization, there is smooth flow and exchange of information across the departments	1	2	3	4	5
4	In my organization, there is strong timely leadership communication provided to employees on work activities	1	2	3	4	5
5	In my organization, effective communication is provided to employees during times of change processes	1	2	3	4	5
6.	In my organization clear and consistent communication channels are provided to employees	1	2	3	4	5
7.	In my organization, constructive communication approaches that facilitate early resolution to conflicts are provided to employees	1	2	3	4	5
8.	In my organization, there are frequent meetings attended by all employees without discrimination	1	2	3	4	5

Section D: Performance Management Systems on Employee Performance

S/N	Statements/rating	1	2	3	4	5
1	In my organization, goals and objectives on work activities are clearly stipulated to all employees	1	2	3	4	5
2	In my organization, there are regular performance reviews and appraisals are provided to employees to assess their performance.	1	2	3	4	5
3	In my organization, training and development opportunities are provided to employees to enhance their competences.	1	2	3	4	5
4	In my organization, there are Performance metrics provided to employees in their departments to guide their performance.	1	2	3	4	5
5	In my organization, recognition and rewards are provided to employees who excel in their duties and responsibilities.	1	2	3	4	5
6	In my organization, there is employee satisfaction and engagement among employees.	1	2	3	4	5
7	In my organization, there are Performance improvement plans provided to all employees.	1	2	3	4	5

Section E: Employee engagement on Employee performance

S/N	Statements/ratings	1	2	3	4	5
1.	In my organization, there are adequate Career development opportunities provided to all employees.	1	2	3	4	5
2.	In my organization, there is Collaboration and teamwork among employees in carrying out their work activities.	1	2	3	4	5
3.	In my organization, employees are autonomous and empowered in their work assignments.	1	2	3	4	5
4.	In my organization, employees participate actively in decision making with the management.	1	2	3	4	5
5.	In my organization, employee retention among employees has led to improved continuous performance.	1	2	3	4	5

6	In my organization, there is work-life balance allowing employees opportunities to have time for their private family activities.	1	2	3	4	5
7.	In my organization, attendance and punctuality in organizational activities is upheld by all employees.	1	2	3	4	5

Section F: Change management on Employee performance

S/N	Statements/ratings	1	2	3	4	5
1	In my organization, the management creates awareness on organizational changes in time.	1	2	3	4	5
2	In my organization, the leaders support change initiatives openly without fear or favour.	1	2	3	4	5
3	In my organization, there is employee engagement and involvement in change process without favour or discrimination	1	2	3	4	5
4	In my organization, employees are trained and counselled before implementing any change initiatives.	1	2	3	4	5
5	In my organization, adequate resources are allocated to support new changes con programmes and activities.	1	2	3	4	5
6	In my organization, change readiness assessment is provided to employees in time.	1	2	3	4	5
17	In my organization, employees are prepared to be adaptable through continuous learning programmes.	1	2	3	4	5

Section G: Government policies on Employee performance

S/N	Statements/ratings	1	2	3	4	5
1	In my organization, Policy awareness is provided to all employees.	1	2	3	4	5
2	In my organization, Employees adhere to government regulations and compliance requirements.	1	2	3	4	5
3	In my organization, there is fairness and equity in terms of employee treatment and opportunities at work without discrimination.	1	2	3	4	5
4	In my organization, employee benefits and compensation are determined by the national government.	1	2	3	4	5
5	In my organization, working conditions are stipulated by government requirements.	1	2	3	4	5
6	In my organization, there are clear policies on work-life balance and flexible work arrangements.	1	2	3	4	5
7	In my organization, training and development opportunities for workers are determined by the government.	1	2	3	4	5
8	In my organization, the government stipulates implementation and adherence to health and safety for managers and employees.	1	2	3	4	5

Section H: Employee performance in Local Government

S/N	Statements/ratings	1	2	3	4	5
1	In m organization, employees provide good quality of work to the public.	1	2	3	4	5
2	In m organization, employees are productive and efficient in carrying out their duties.	1	2	3	4	5
3	In my organization, employees' service delivery is satisfactory.	1	2	3	4	5
4	In my organization, here is sustainability of services provided by employees.	1	2	3	4	5
5	In my organization, there is timely completion of assigned tasks and projects by employees.	1	2	3	4	5
6	In my organization, there is effective collaboration across departments among employees.	1	2	3	4	5
7	In my organization, there is innovation and problem solving among employees.	1	2	3	4	5
8	In my organization, there is high employee retention.	1	2	3	4	5

Thank you for your Cooperation

APPENDIX III: INFORMED CONSENT FOR MANAGEMENT/ADMINISTRATION DEPARTMENT

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RESEARCH ETHICS COMMITTEE (REC)**

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Do you agree?

Do you disagree?

Name of participant Signature of participant _____
Thumb print Date

Name of person obtaining _____
Consent Signature _____
Thumb print Date

Names of witness _____
Signature of witness _____
Thumb print

Leave blank (for REC Office only):
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TELEPHONE: +256 772426581

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APPENDIX IV: INTERVIEW GUIDE FOR MANAGEMENT /ADMINISTRATION DEPARTMENT

i. Organizational Culture and Employee Performance

1. Communication Patterns and Employee Performance

Objective: To examine the relationship between communication patterns and employee performance in Kasese and Kabarole Districts local government.

- a. How would you describe the communication patterns within the local government and their impact on the performance of employees?
- b. Explain of how clear or unclear communication has affected the performance of employees in your department or team.
- c. In your experience, how do the communication methods between management and staff influence employees' motivation and their work efficiency?

2. Performance Management Mechanisms and Employee Performance

Objective: To determine the relationship between performance management mechanisms and employee performance in Kasese and Kabarole Districts local governments.

- a. How effective do you think the current performance management systems are in enhancing employee productivity and performance?
- b. Share any examples where performance management mechanisms either positively or negatively impacted the performance of employees.
- c. In your view, how do the performance appraisal processes align with the motivation and development of employees in your department?

3. Employee Engagement and Employee Performance

Objective: To assess the relationship between employee engagement and employee performance in Kasese and Kabarole Districts local governments.

- a. How would you define employee engagement, and to what extent do you think it influences performance within your team or department?
- b. What initiative or practice that has successfully increased employee engagement and resulted in improved performance?
- c. What are the key challenges in maintaining high levels of employee engagement, and how do they affect overall employee performance in the local government?

4. Change Management and Employee Performance

Objective: To establish the relationship between change management and employee performance in Kasese and Kabarole Districts local governments.

- a. How does the local government manage organizational changes, and how do these changes influence employee performance?
- b. Share an example of a recent change initiative and how it impacted employee performance, either positively or negatively.
- c. In your experience, what role does effective change management play in maintaining or improving employee performance during transitions?

5. Government Policies and Employee Performance

Objective: To find out the moderating effect of government policies on employee performance in the Kasese and Kabarole districts local governments.

- a. To what extent do government policies (such as staffing, budgeting, and administrative procedures) affect the performance of employees in your local government?
- b. How do you perceive the role of government policies in creating an environment that either supports or hinders employee performance?
- c. Describe any specific government policies that have had a direct impact on improving or reducing employee performance within your department.

ii. Employee performance in Local Government

1. Describe any specific strategies or practices that have helped employees in your organization consistently deliver high-quality work to the public? What challenges, if any, have you encountered in ensuring quality service delivery
2. What factors do you believe contribute most to the productivity and efficiency of employees in your organization, and what actions have been taken to address any productivity-related challenges?
3. What measures does your organization take to ensure employees consistently meet or exceed public expectations in service delivery? Can you share any feedback from the public regarding the satisfaction with employee performance?
4. How does your organization ensure that employees provide sustainable services over time, especially in the face of resource constraints or external challenges?
5. What systems or practices are in place to ensure that employees complete their tasks and projects on time, and how does management address delays or missed deadlines?
6. What strategies or initiatives have been put in place to foster cross-departmental collaboration, and how has this collaboration influenced the overall performance of employees and the organization?
7. How does your organization encourage innovation and problem-solving among employees? Briefly Share any specific examples of successful innovations or solutions that have contributed to improved employee performance.
8. What factors do you believe contribute most to high employee performance in your organization, and what strategies are in place to ensure employee performance in the long term?

THANK YOU SO MUCH

